

1 **ALOX15b activation in ulcerative colitis.**

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6 Lipid mediators are inflammatory factors that include leukotrienes and prostaglandins and are
7 derived from the eicosanoid arachidonic acid. We describe here transcriptional activation and differential
8 expression of an enzyme functioning in the arachidonic acid biosynthetic pathway, arachidonate
9 15-lipoxygenase, type B (*ALOX15b*) in the blood of humans with active ulcerative colitis. In a cohort of
10 children and young adults with ulcerative colitis, ALOX15B was transcriptionally active in mucosal tissue of
11 the colon. Functionally, ALOX15b is transcriptionally co-regulated with the interleukins IL28a and IL-37, a
12 cytokine whose genetic deficiency results in very early onset inflammatory bowel disease (ulcerative
13 colitis). These data support a role for hematopoietic-derived ALOX15B activity in tissues in propagating
14 rather than countering inflammation.
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